

SMART GOVERNANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF SMART VILLAGES

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Abstract

Purpose – In order to close the digital divide between urban and rural digitalization development our study focuses on the impact of the smart governance concept in Romanian villages and convergence into „Smart Villages”, with its benefits and challenges.

Methodology/approach – The findings of this paper is based on a structured questionnaire conducted on mayors from 358 communes out of 2862 (12.5%) in which 9.262,851 of Romanian reside (46.05%).

Findings – The paper studies the perception of village mayors in regards to smart governance using digital technologies and convergence into “Smart Villages” in a post COVID-19 world.

Research limitations/implications – The questions addressed were not meant directly to discover smart governance readiness in Romanian villages. However, the questionnaire tackles all of the core questions that must be addressed in any Smart Governance model used in villages.

Practical implications – The Smart Governance concept refers to the use of various and innovative information technology solutions in order to improve the decision-making process in public administration, through better collaboration among different stakeholders, including government, citizens and the private sector.

Originality/value – This paper coins a definition for “smart village governance” and contributes to developing a framework for building new, smart governance models addressing the growing challenges of rural communities.

Key words: smart village

Introduction

The digitalization process of the national and global economy, accelerated by the recent COVID-19 pandemic is considered the 4th Industrial Revolution according to Skilton and Hovsepian (2018), having a major impact on private economic actors and public entities, from governments to local public administrations (Reischauer, 2018).

The recent years marked by unprecedented society changes, a new „normal” was shaped by the COVID-10 pandemic, from the „normal way” we spend our free time, interact with others and work. For this reason, the implementation of digital technologies has major consequences in the evolution of modern society, from its impact on the economy, according to Goldfarb, Greenstein, Tucker (2015), labour market (Bejakovic, Mrnjavac, 2020) and the digitalization of public services, which culminates in the Smart Governance concept, present in advanced economies around the world (Pereira, Parycek, Falco, Kleinhans, 2018a).

The Smart Governance concept refers to the use of various and innovative information technology solutions in order to improve the decision-making process in public administration, through better collaboration among different stakeholders, including government, citizens and the private sector, according to Pereira, Parycek, Falco and Kleinhans (2018b).

Smart governance moreso in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic has an important role in supporting citizen initiatives, through providing a digital framework in which complex interactions between governments, citizens and other stakeholders can take place. In this regard, Smart Governance

according to Viswanadham, Vedula (2010) can be considered one of the 6 pillars of a true Smart Village, alongside: Smart Mobility (Docherty, Marsden, Anable, 2018), Smart Living (Asriadi, Jamaluddin, Abdullahi, 2021), Smart Environment (Aziiza, Susanto, 2020), Smart Citizen (Soon, 2016) and Smart Economy (Adamowicz, Zwolinska-Ligaj, 2020).

Compared to the other 5 Smart Village pillars, Smart Governance is primary dedicated towards digitizing and improving administrative public services, and must be directly implemented by public central and local authorities, according to Scholl and Scholl (2014).

The European Union, was the first major public institution to define a smart village as reliant on a participatory approach, or smart governance: "Smart villages are communities in rural areas that use innovative solutions to improve their resilience, building on local strengths and opportunities"¹. They rely on a participatory approach to develop and implement their strategy to improve their economic, social and/or environmental conditions, in particular by mobilising solutions offered by digital technologies"².

Smart governance approaches are now leading public administration reforms in many developed European economies, such as Austria, United Kingdom and Italy who are seeing great results in engaging citizens in participatory governance, which brings more insight on the needs of the community and many times solutions to those problems directly from their citizens (Gupta, 2008).

Authors such as Pereira et. al Pereira, Parycek, Falco, Kleinhans (2018), Eremia, Toma, Sanduleac (2017), and Winkowska, Szpilko, Pejic (2019) demonstrated that using various collaborative and transparent information and communication technologies for governing can improve internal processes, increase transparency, reduce corruption and enhance communication between public servants and citizens in cities, however there is little research on the perception, readiness and evolution towards smart governance in villages.

Our paper is focused on smart governance in Romanian villages, as an emerging field of study of the impact of digitalization in villages by using information technology in order to enhance the decision making process in village halls, and transform the way public services are delivered in the digital age. More specifically, our scope is to provide a clearer view on the perception, readiness and evolution towards smart governance in the Romanian Smart Villages of tomorrow, by conducting a smart governance survey in 358 Romanian villages, out of the 2862 village commons in Romania, in which close to 10 million citizens live, or 44% of Romanian population vs. 25% the EU average.³

The paper also aims at contributing to the development of a new smart governance model by addressing the challenges of the digital society, information sharing, citizen engagement, collaborative governance and transparency in villages, the smallest human communities that in many aspects are lagging behind cities in terms of digitization, according to Salemin, Strijker, Bosworth (2017a) and Townsend, Wallace, Fairhurst, (2015a).

Smart Villages in Romania

What are Smart Villages?

On a global level, the concept of smart villages dates back in the period of 2014-2017, with the first smart village initiatives occurring in Central Africa, Asia and South America (Holmes, 2017). In the European Union the emergence of the "Smart Village concept" is associated with the "Cork 2.0 Declaration for a Better Life in Rural Areas" from 2016 (Visvizi, Lytras, Mudri, 2019), when through a 10 points manifesto in improving the quality of life in rural areas across the European Union, digitalization and connectivity were seen as tools in order to achieve the goals set by the 10 points manifesto.

Further steps by the European Union were seen in the following year, by the European Commission's publication of "EU Action for Smart Villages" in 2017 (Stojanova, Lentini, Niederer, Egger, Cvar, Kos,

¹ Concept, issues and prospects for EU rural areas: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/689349/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)689349_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/689349/EPRS_BRI(2021)689349_EN.pdf)

² Concept, issues and prospects for EU rural areas: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/689349/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)689349_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/689349/EPRS_BRI(2021)689349_EN.pdf)

³ Ziarul Financiar articole: 44% of Romanian live in rural areas: <https://www.zf.ro/eveniment/circa-44-din-populatia-romaniei-traieste-in-mediul-rural-media-uniunii-europene-este-de-25-14918560>

Duh, 2021), where the E.U. defined policy areas and funds for smart villages, adopting an integrative approach towards them (Zavratnik, Kos, Duh, 2018).

Smart villages don't have a legal definition in the national or E.U. legislation, but they are the villages that usually stand out in the rural landscape by being aware of rural issues and open to adopting innovative solutions. They share a positive and interested attitude towards digitalization, by being eager to adopt digital innovations and having digital skills, be it technical, organizational or communicative skills, which is in contrast to the more traditional and many times reticent to innovate rural communities (Zerrer, Sept, 2020)

Smart villages are the most innovative villages in a country, innovation that is given by the implementation of various public sector digital platforms and technological solutions, which accompanied by a modern way of thinking about public services and public servants brings many benefits to citizens from rural areas and closing the gap between the urban-rural digital divide according to Saleminck, Strijker, Bosworth (2017b).

Research methodology

In partnership with the Association of Romanian Communes (ACOR) we have conducted a quantitative study by sending a structured questionnaire, addressing important questions in relation to digital development in Romanian communes via email, directly to the members of the ACOR, comprised of mayors from 2862 village communes, which accounts for 87.13% of Romania's landmass and 9.262,851 of it's residents (46.05%).⁴

Out of the 2862 communes, we have received answers from 358 communes, which represents a response and representation rate of 12.50% from the total number of communes in Romania, which brings a statistical significance of 95%, with a margin or error less than 5% to our study.

The questionnaire was constructed by the authors of this paper, in consultations with Mr. Sergiu Tara, Executive President of ACOR and Mr. Damian George, Vice President of ACOR and Mayor of Ciugud Village, Romanians first Smart Village⁵, with the scope of discovering the level of rural digitalization readiness and usage of the most basic digital software solutions in order to develop a "Smart Village and Smart Governance Guidelines for Romanian villages" which aims at supporting Romanian villages in their transition towards smart villages and smart governance.

It's important to note that the questions addressed were not meant directly to discover smart governance readiness in Romanian villages, but the overall convergence of Romanian villages towards the smart village model. However, the questionnaire tackles all of the core questions that must be addressed in any Smart Governance model used in a village common, such as Service improvement, Administrative efficiency and Citizen centrality, all supported and enhanced by ICT.

Romanian villages

The respondents of our study, which has a statistical significance of 95%, and a margin or error less than 5% are diverse, such as the rural landscape in Romania.

As seen in Table 1, the majority of village commons to our survey, comprising 67.32% have 11-25% public servants, followed by 20.11% of villages with 26 – 50 public servants and 9.78% with 1 - 10 public servants.

Table 1. Number of village hall public servants

Public servants	Responses	Percentage
1 - 10	35	9.78%
11 - 25	241	67.32%
26 - 50	72	20.11%
>60	11	3.07%

⁴ ACOR members: <https://www.acor.ro/comune-membre/>

⁵ Ciugud, the first Romanian Smart Village: https://adevarul.ro/locale/alba-iulia/o-comuna-ardeal-devenit-exemplu-bune-practici-polonia-romanii-vor-exporta-conceptul-smart-village-1_6159aba25163ec4271ee1e47/index.html

According to Table 2, 60.89% or most village commons in Romania are middle size with 2001 - 5000 residents, followed by smaller commons up to 2000 residents (22.35%). Large rural communities, are usually found at the outskirts of cities and comprise 16.75% of total village commons, with communities with 50001-8000 inhabitants (12.57%) and with more than 8000 residents (4.19%)

Table 2. Number of citizens in the village common

Nr. of citizens	Responses	Percentage
1 - 2000	80	22.35%
2001 - 5000	218	60.89%
50001 - 8000	45	12.57%
>8001	15	4.19%

Digital strategy

Until recently, in Romania having a digital strategy was seen as a necessity only in cities, and even so we have instances where cities don't yet have a coherent digitalization strategy in place. This is important to mention because villages and villagers alike are looking at cities for inspiration in regards to how a digital rural community and local administration should look like.

As until recently villages in Romania didn't have a complete working example on how a digital strategy can be implemented in rural communities and which are the quantifiable benefits of its implementation, we can see that according to Table 3 only 6.98% of villages have a clear digital strategy in place in order to develop themselves into smart villages.

Table 3. Digital strategy development in Romanian Villages

Existence of a digital strategy	Responses	Percentage
There is a clear strategy	25	6.98%
There are some ideas	199	55.59%
No	110	30.73%
I don't know	24	6.70%

It is however encouraging to see that 55.59% of Romanian villages have some ideas on how their commune could benefit from ICT and ultimately be transformed into a smart village, meaning it's only a matter of time for them until a clear digital strategy framework will be defined.

For the rest 37.43% of Romanian villages, out of which 30.73% don't have any ideas in developing a digital strategy for their community, and 6.70% don't know what a digital strategy implies, it's important to note that the Smart Village concept is still a very new one in Romania and until recently there were not many public funds destined for supporting digitalization projects in villages, neither a clear demand from citizens in rural areas, as many villages in Romania are still lacking a good road infrastructure, sewerage and water systems, and understandably you cannot think about a smart village if the commune doesn't have access to the most basic living amenities.

As the vast majority of village mayors (77.93%) are saying that 70% or more of village hall activities can be digitalized (See Figure 1), we can assume that after the necessary investments in road infrastructure, sewerage and water systems take place, digital investments will follow, and more of the 37.43% of Romanian villages with no digital strategy will start developing and ultimately implementing one.

It's also encouraging to see that the most common preconception that villages are reticent to adopt digital solutions is wrong, as seen in Figure 1, the majority of villages are familiar with the ways digitalization can positively impact their community, and so the slow adoption of digital solutions in villages if compared with cities is not about reluctance towards digitalization, but mostly to do with other factors, as seen in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. The extent to which the activity of the Village Hall can be digitized

According to Figure 2, digital literacy of village hall public servants is seen as the main digital transformation impediment by 72.35% of mayors, followed by not enough public servants or time towards digital projects (37.43%), insufficiency hardware devices (32.30%), workstations (19.83%), bad or non existent internet connection (12.29%) and insufficient mobile devices (9.22%).

Internet connection in the modern age contributes to the sustainability of rural life Townsend, Wallace, Fairhurst, (2015b), and as Romania has one of the fastest and cheapest broadband internet connections in the world⁶ is in strong contrast with other developing nations, where poor broadband infrastructure is the main impediment for developing the digital infrastructure (Yates, Gulati, Weiss, 2011), (Pentland, Fletcher, Hasson, 2004), as in Romania bad or non existent internet connection (12.29%) is one of the smallest digitalization impediment faced by villages, according to Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Which of the following factors are an impediment in the digitalization process

In terms of who is the main coordinator in the digitalization process, as seen in Table 4, in 31.56% of cases, we have a dedicated public servant or more than one (24.86%) , followed by external consultants with 21.79%, and ultimately the mayor with 20.39%, dismantling the common belief that the village mayor who most times is the driver of digital transformation, as a policy maker is also the coordinator of the digital transformation process.

⁶ Connectivity Studies 2021: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/desi-connectivity#ecl-inpage-kvv2e3tf>

Table 4. Who can coordinate the digitization process in the village hall

Who coordinates the digitization process	Responses	Percentage
Mayor	73	20.39%
One employee of the village hall	113	31.56%
More then one employee of the village hall	89	24.86%
External consultant	78	21.79%
No one	5	1.40%

Service improvement

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, we have seen an acceleration of central and local taxes that could be payed online⁷ this is also the case in villages, as seen in Table 5 where 33.50% of them already accept banking methods, through "Ghiseul.ro" the national fee and taxes platform, or local digital solutions in which citizens can pay their local taxes online.

Table 5. Can citizens pay their local taxes online?

Paying taxes online	Responses	Percentage
Yes	120	33.50%
No, but we want to	176	49.20%
No	62	17.30%

The trend of using digital payment solutions for local taxes is expected to accelerate in the following years, as 49.20% of village halls that don't yet provide means of paying local taxes online, do want the implementation of such systems.

In the case of the 17.30% of villages that don't have and are not yet interested in developing solutions to let citizens pay their local taxes online, we can assume that one of the digital impediments enumerated in the previous Figure 2 are causing this situation.

In Romania, also helped by the COVID-19 pandemic, 35.47% of villages already use e-registrations forms and online appointments, as seen in Table 6, and other 39.39% of villages are interested in e-registrations forms and online appointments, only 25.14% of villages don't see a necessity for such applications.

Table 6. Do you use applications to receive online notification, documents, appointments, etc.?

Receiving notifications, documents, appointments online	Responses	Percentage
Yes	127	35.47%
No	90	25.14%
No, but we want to	141	39.39%

In the digital economy and digital age, cybersecurity and data protection must be an implied service provided by all institutions and for all public service, this is not a desideratum, but in fact the law that villages must also abide by.

As seen in Table 7, it's concerning to see that 61.50% of Romanian villages don't use an official email address to communicate with citizens and most importantly securely store their personal information, which according the G.D.P.R. law, also in effect in Romania, implies that all institutions and private companies from the European Union must guarantee the safely of citizen private date, this cannot be done by using personal email addresses, as the village hall doesn't have control over them and cannot monitor and secure the official communication between public servants and citizens.

⁷ Delloite report: <https://www2.deloitte.com/ro/ro/pages/about-deloitte/articles/expertii-deloitte-criza-a-accelerat-digitalizarea-dar-incertitudinea-si-lipsa-de-transparenta-vor-afecta-in-continuare-mediul-de-afaceri-urmeaza-informtizarea-administratiei-fiscale-si-intensificarea-controalelor-in-zone-de-risc.html>

Table 7. Are village hall public servants using an official email address?

Using an official email address?	Responses	Percentage
Yes	138	38.50%
No, but we want to	89	24.90%
No	131	36.60%

In this case, we are not talking about a lack of financial funds for enabling the use of official email addresses, as such costs are minimal, but an underestimation or a lack of knowledge on the dangers of cyber crimes, theft of personal data and importance of using official email addresses for safeguarding citizen private data, as seen in the requirements of the law no. 190 from 2018 on measures to implement in order to comply with E.U. directive 679 from 2016 in regards to the general data protection regulation (GDPR)⁸. This however is not only a problem that only villages must comply to, but also a responsibility from the Romanian State to enforce the GDPR law in all institutions.

Table 8. The use an application for electronic and document management

Electronic registration and document management system	Responses	Percentage
Yes	151	42.18%
No	103	28.77%
No, but we want to	104	29.05%

Administrative efficiency

The most common administrative efficiency digital solution found in Romanian villages are those related to electronic registration and document management systems (DMS), where 42.18% of villages are already using them, 29.05% being interested in their implementations and 28.77% with no interest in the matter.

The recent interest of Romanian villages in adopting electronic registration and document management systems has also to do with the development of such solutions from companies like „Registra”⁹ on a "Software as a Service" model (SaaS), where village halls are paying a yearly subscription fee to access those digital solutions, making the technology more affordable in the short term, as villages don't have an acquisition cost.

Digital administrative solutions, such as those developed by Registra for more than 750 cities and villages across Romania¹⁰ are highly standardized digital solutions destined for city and village halls, as an integrated e-governance solution, with modules such as: electronic registration, document management, citizen tickets, electronic forms, online complaints or requests, online appointments, online payment management, citizen portal, automatic publication of public information, managing third party software solutions (smart meters, parking systems, street lighting, etc), however few villages are using all the modules of a such advanced digital administrative solution¹¹.

One of the most common ways a document management system improves efficiency in the public administrations is by tracking workflows and documents, which is the case of 25.42% of villages who implemented such applications and other 37.43% that are interested in their implementation, as seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Application for tracking workflows and documents at the village hall

Using applications for tracking workflows and documents	Responses	Percentage
Yes	91	25.42%
No	133	37.15%
No, but we want to	134	37.43%

⁸ GDPR law applied in Romania: https://www.dataprotection.ro/?page=Legea_nr_190_2018&lang=ro

⁹ Registra DMS Software solution: <https://registra.ro/>

¹⁰ Registra DMS Software solution: <https://registra.ro/>

¹¹ E-Governance ICT solution from Registra: <https://registra.ro/#mol>

Tracking workows and documents can be offered as a module in the more complex electronic registration and document management system, or be offered as a standalone solution, which however doesn't have the complexity of a fully e-governance digital solution.

Keeping track on inventory items brings a new meaning through the use of a digital platform, or mobile device, as citizens can improve village asset management by sending notifications to the village hall, such as intervention requirements if the utility infrastructure (electricity, lights, etc) is malfunctioning, or requirements, such as connecting to the utility network, which can be processed into digital workows thorough the use of a tracking workows and documents system.

As seen in Table 10, in the case of 24.86% of villages, such systems already exists in various digital forms, while other 41.90% of villages are interested in using them. In these instance, administrative efficiency is improved by having better asset management capabilities, as communication with citizens is improved by ICT solutions.

Table 10. The use of application for inventory/asset management

Using an inventory/asset management application	Responses	Percentage
Yes	89	24.86%
No	119	33.24%
No, but we want to	150	41.90%

Citizen centricity

Citizen centricity starts with transparency, which implies free and unrestricted access to any information of public interest, as defined by law no. 544 from 2001, meaning access to: the organizational structure, the attributions of each department, the functioning program, the audience program of the village hall, contact details of the public authority, financial statements, etc¹².

According to Table 11 the way 92.70% of village halls are complying with this law is by publishing that information and documents through their official website, and 7.2% of them are probably still using a notice board, which by our modern understanding of free access to public information is not sufficient. It is however worth mentioning that out of the 7.2%, 6.1% of villages want to develop an official website.

Table 11. Do you have an official village hall website?

Official website	Responses	Percentage
Yes	332	92.70%
No, but we want to	22	6.1%
No	4	1.1%

In terms of how a citizen centric approach must be seen at a rural level, is by having a clear insight on the needs of the community and many times we are seeing that the needs of the citizens are in relation to subordinate village hall intuitions, such as the public library, village school and sports facilities.

In Figure 3 we are seeing the beginning of citizen centricity in villages, as discussions are starting to emerge on the needs of developing digital systems such as online public library (29.89%), public gym appointments (25.99%) and school grades management solutions (25.70%), type of solutions that involves a higher knowledge of citizen needs and a tighter citizen-village hall partnership in governance, which according to Figure 3 is only in it's early phase, but the idea of participatory governance and citizen centricity is starting to get momentum, as seen in Table 12.

¹² Law regarding access to public information: <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/31413>

Fig. 3. Do you have the following applications at subordinate institutions?

One of the most encouraging findings of our study is that village halls are overwhelmingly in favor (89.66%) of participatory governance and tools to develop social and civic dialogue with citizens and NGO's, as seen in Table 12.

Table 12. Do you consider it necessary to develop tools for interaction between NGOs/social partners and public administration authorities and institutions in order to encourage social and civic dialogue?

Answer	Responses	Percentage
Yes	321	89.66%
No	33	9.22%

Only time will tell us how many of those 89.66% forward thinking villages will embrace citizen centricity and participatory governance, not only in concept, but in practice, practice that also implies a higher local civic spirit and active role of citizens in the village hall decision making processes.

Conclusions

Challenges in becoming a Smart Village

1. Digital strategy planification

Defining some ideas of tackling local development issues with the help of ICT, into a coherent digital strategy is a challenge for most Romanian villages, as seen in the previous Table 3, where we see that only 6.98% of villages developed a digital strategy.

Moreover, as a quarter of Romanian villages don't have access to a sewage system or access to other basic utilities¹³, defining a digital strategy might be of a low priority, until basic village infrastructure is developed.

2. Digital literacy

As the main impediment (72.35%) of creating a digital strategy, identified by the mayors in our study, as seen in Table 4 is the digital literacy of public servants, measures must be taken in order to develop solutions that can not only increase the digital literacy of public servants but of rural citizens as well, Romania, according to the latest DESI report from 2021 being a country of extremes, with the highest percentage of ICT graduates per capita in the European Union, of 6.3% of total graduates vs. 3.9% the U.E. average, but also with one of the populations with the lowest above basic digital competencies, of 10% vs 31%, the E.U. average¹⁴.

¹³ Eurostat report on indoor flushing toilet: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

¹⁴ DESI Report from 2021: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/desi-romania>

3. Demographic crisis

By 2050, Eurostat estimates that 25% of Romania's rural population will disappear¹⁵. According to the latest statistics, villages are rapidly depopulating in Romania, people moving to cities or emigrating in other E.U. countries in search for better employment opportunities and standard of living.

In Romania living in a rural area is seen as having less opportunities and a lower standard of living than in cities, which are the main causes of depopulation.

However, if, such as the case of Ciugud village (See Chapter 4) access to the living amenities are improved (good roads, sewage and water system, etc.) and better employment opportunities are provided in villages, those demographic trends can be expected to change for the better.

4. Funding for digital change in rural areas

One of the reasons many villages postponed the discussion about digital strategy had also to do with available funding for the digital transformation in rural areas, as the European Union only launched "EU Action for Smart Villages initiative" in 2017¹⁶ and the Romania government only started promoting smart villages strategies starting from 2020¹⁷. As funding for digitalization strategies will start to emerge, so will the village interest increase in pursuing digital transformation strategies.

Challenges in adopting the Smart Governance model

Convergence towards smart villages The village convergence towards a smart governance model implies not only a greater openness of governance and citizen centricity, but also the implementation of ICT solution that help keep citizen engagement high, by providing a means of communication and a more efficient method at enhancing transparency and trust in a digital enabled participatory governance model.

In these sens, even if the minimum technical requirements of providing a e-governance framework can be summed up by adopting a complete electronic registration and document management systems (DMS), as described previously, smart governance is only enabled by such digital solution, not driven by them.

The main driver of change being the village hall and their public servants that must plan in advance such paradigm shifts in governance, planning that must be drawn up beforehand in a coherent digital smart village strategy, which for many villages pose a challenge, whether it's because of a lack of digital literacy, funding for digital transformation or other impediments.

As seen in Table 12, 89.66% of village mayors are overwhelmingly in favor of a more open social and civic dialogue with citizens and NGO's, but as citizen centricity implies governmental transparency, which brings greater accountability and reduces corruption, it's idealistic to think that such changes can occur without any resistance from public officials.

Only time will tell us how high transparency resistance will be, and in which form it will manifest itself, because resistance can also mean blocking the interoperability and sharing of public sector data, which not only makes governing and public services more efficient and transparent, but also more accountable (Pina, Torres, Acerete, 2007).

Final conclusions

Although the concept of smart governance in the context of smart villages is fairly new, the concept, with it's two core elements, of involving the local community and the use of digital tools in order to develop and enhance public servants and citizens partnership in governance, for the ultimate goal of achieving participatory governance, is beginning to gain traction and support is starting to emerge from

¹⁵ Population change in the E.U. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/ddn-20210520-1>

¹⁶ EU Action for Smart Villages: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/food-farming-fisheries/key_policies/documents/rur-dev-small-villages_en.pdf

¹⁷ Ciugud is becoming a case study for implementing the Smart Village concept in Romania: <https://zi-are.com/stiri/eveniment/comuna-ciugud-din-alba-devine-studiu-de-caz-in-romania-pentru-conceptul-de-smart-village-ministru-vom-propune-ca-ideea-de-sat-inteligent-sa-devina-program-national-1618743>

the Romanian State, the European Union, and ACOR, which helped the researches of this study through consultations and access to the 358 village mayors of this study.

As the paper shows, village mayors recognize the benefits of digitalization in raising efficiency, as 77.93% of them are saying that 70% or more of village hall activities can be digitalized (See Figure 1) and 89.66% of mayors are overwhelmingly in favor of social dialogue with NGOs/social partners (See Table 12), it is therefore an immediate opportunity to seize this momentum and find solutions to the widest common impediment that village halls face in the adoption of ICT solutions which according to Figure 2, is represented by digital literacy of village hall public servants.

Having digital literate public servants will not only lead to the adoption of digital solutions in order to improve services, administrative efficiency and enabling a digital citizen-centric approach, but also represents a matter of reducing national security risks.

In terms of national security risks, most Romanian villages (See Table 7) don't know the dangers of cybercrimes and the most basic forms of cybersecurity, which is seen in the fact that 61.50% of them don't even use official email addresses in their communication with citizens and most importantly don't securely store the personal data of those 9,262,851 Romanian citizens (46.05%) living in rural areas.¹⁸

If a digitalization guide or framework for smart villages coupled with digital workshops are not provided to village halls in Romania in the following period, we may see a growing resistance to digital transformation, which will certainly lead to a poor absorption of the European funds destined for smart village projects and a wider urban-rural digital divide.

In the end, ICT only enables and does not drive the smart governance model in villages, as the true "SMART" component in any community remains its people, who can be drivers, supporters and users of digital-enabled solutions, which builds on local strengths and opportunities in order to improve citizens' quality of life and engagement in governance.

It is therefore of utmost importance that the Romanian State, the Association of Romanian Communes and other relevant NGOs work together in order to increase digital literacy in villages, both in public servants, as well as citizens.

Future research directions

As the study found out that the main impediment in developing a coherent digital strategy in Romanian villages is represented by digital literacy of public servants, based on our current findings and in partnership with Holisun, an IT R&D Romanian company¹⁹ and the Association of Romanian Communes we will develop the first "*Smart Village and Smart Governance Guidelines for Romanian villages*", after consultation with a focus group compiled of the most digitalized 30 Romanian villages that will take place in 2022. The following paper will present the results of implementing the "*Smart Village and Smart Governance Guidelines for Romanian villages*" through a set of digital literacy indicators that will be collected before and after the guidelines are implemented in villages that will be part of the project.

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